

**THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS RELATED TO TERMINOLOGY IN
WORLD LINGUISTICS**

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Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical views related to terminology in various systematic languages and world linguistics.

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Introduction: Currently, due to the socio-economic development in our country, great attention is being paid to every field, including changes and reforms in the sports system. As a result of such updates, the flow of international terms and neologisms entering the lexical level of the language is accelerating. This process, in turn, requires that experts in the field know the exact expression of concepts and terms related to their profession, and have full knowledge of their content and essence.

At the moment, specialists are conducting large-scale research in order to study the formation, development and development of certain terminological systems and their specific features in different systematic languages. Despite this, controversial problems in terminology have not lost their relevance and are currently waiting for their solution. In this sense, various innovations, developed scientific-theoretical views, and research results surrounding the concept of the term attract not only linguists, but also specialists in other fields and remain one of the topical issues.

The appearance of the word term in different systematic languages in a series of periods, although we can roughly note the history of origin, the Latin word terminus, which appeared in the Middle Ages, and the ancient Greek logos ("concept", "the "limot" meaning) we can note the emergence of the word terminology, which is formed from the combination of the words, more precisely compared to the word term.

The concept of the term was used in several senses, first as a deity of boundaries, and later as boundary stone, final or finished place, destination. By the Middle Ages, the word terminus was used in the sense of identifying and marking

(something). In the field of linguistics, there is a lot of information about the origin of the term terminology and its use in spoken and written speech. This concept was first used by the German linguist Schutz in 1786. In the French language, this term appeared in the 18th century. If we turn to the Oxford dictionary, we can see that the word terminology was first used in English in 1801. The authors of the Longman dictionary explained the word terminus as "term". In the explanatory dictionaries of the Russian language, the word "termin" appeared from the first half of the 18th century. As a result of historical development, in the first half of the 19th century, the word "term" was used in Russian in a slightly different form in oral and written speech, that is, this concept was used as a means of expressing common names. Thus, the concept of "term" has become a word that has a specific meaning, a specific definition.

Another innovation in world linguistics at the beginning of the 19th century is the processes related to the creation and creation of terms. Linguists began to implement different approaches to the creation of the term, to clarify its linguistic features.

In particular, G. Kittridge compared terms with mathematical formulas and noted: "Terms are used when people communicate for a specific purpose." In our opinion, at the current stage of development, such ideas are not approved by terminological scientists. The main reason for this is that expressions, signs, scientific and other technological terms make up a large part of the lexical units in general use.

U.G. Paul said that the narrowing of the meaning of words creates the basis for the emergence of terms. A.A. Potebnya, one of the scientists who approached this issue from the other side, stated that such problems do not affect the terminology. At the time, U.G. Paul's ideas may have been proven, but now new inventions and ideas are creating the basis for the emergence of terms, not as a result of the narrowing of the meaning of the word, but as a result of progress.

In world linguistics, some linguists compare the terms to jargon. For example; J. Vandries, L. Smith's ideas and views were a clear example of this. J. Vandries said: "Technological languages either create new words or cause words in ordinary communication to be used in a special sense."

In his research, N.V. Krumevsky connected the terms with the science of natural science and expressed his thoughts about the natural terminology of the language. Based on the natural terminology of the language, the scientist records the names of animals and plants that are gradually changing, and at the same time emphasizes that "natural terminology" does not replace "artificial terminology" at all. I.A. Beaudoin de Courtenay opposed Krumevsky's ideas and noted that "due to

conscious exchanges, many new expressions, signs, scientific and other technological terms appear only artificially."

A. Shirmer tried to determine the specific criteria of terminology and study it as a specific field in linguistics, demarcating it from other areas of the language. He carried out his scientific research on the basis of German language material. A. Schirmer divides the vocabulary of the German language into two according to its expression in speech: universal (mass) lexicon and special lexicon. In his research, A. Shirmer included lexemes used in several fields, including the educational field related to the creative activity of people, as well as legal-political, art and several other fields. A. Shirmer has shown a number of important features of terminology in his research. However, due to the fact that more emphasis is placed on the interdisciplinary integration of terminology in his works, the limitation of terminology as a professional (occupational) lexicon, as well as the phenomena of determinologizing, reterminologizing and terminologizing that occur in the terminology of fields, are not sufficiently substantiated.

In his research, Eggerbrecht connects terms with the science of philosophy and defines them as follows: "A term is a word that creates meaning only on the basis of a specific interpretation, in a specific, strict order." Eggerbrecht specifically notes that the term should be considered as a lexeme with a dominant denotative meaning. At the moment, some terms have a connotative feature, that is, it is appropriate to understand their meaning not according to their lexical form, but according to what concept they express. On the basis of Eggerbrecht's opinion, such a conclusion is reached that the word that is actually the basis of the term represents an important factor. One of the correct opinions of this scientist is that the significant amount of terminological units consists mainly of lexemes formed from nouns. Since the terms express the names of specific processes, events and actions, they are mainly reserved for a special network consisting of nouns. After all, in any scientific and technical terminological system, the principle of striving for accuracy and conciseness is followed.

Swiss linguist Charles Bally explains the difference between scientific language and scientific terminology in his research as follows. The first, that is, scientific language is superior in that it is a specific type of expression, while scientific terminology is preferred through a special dictionary. Sh. Balli assesses terminology as: "a set of words that do not belong to the common language, and express certain objective and logical aspects of things with absolute precision." As a result of the scientist's careful observation of common terms in his researches within the spheres related to him and not related to him, he notes that scientific terms are different from professional (vocational) terms, and linguistic features

such as diversity, emotionality, imagery in scientific terms and states that standards do not exist.

And Lars Gurmund compares the terms to a "weapon" used within a discipline. In addition, he notes that the structure of the terminological system of each subject corresponds to the internal structure of this subject to a certain extent.

O. Nybekken is another scientist who is distinguished by his unique views in the field of terminology. Nybecken notes the concept of "technological English" as the language of science, that is, the language of science, as opposed to the common English used for communication, and while acknowledging that this concept is relatively stable, it is words of a more international character. emphasizes that he is enriched with Since technical terms are the basis of technological English, O. Nybekken classifies them based on their main characteristics as follows:

- 1) clear and serious description;
- 2) targeting (orientation) in internal and external spheres;
- 3) possession of specific characteristics to be proportional to language standards

[Nybekken is; B.36].

The first two classifications stated by O. Nybekken are controversial and can be explained in terms of the scope of application and the narrowness of their meaning. In the last classification, O. Nybekken assumes that the structure of terms should be implemented on the basis of certain linguistic factors.

By the middle of the 20th century, controversial processes, conflicting opinions and views began to rise in the field of terminology. By this time, a number of basic concepts such as "terminological system" by D.S. Lotte and "terminological field" by L.A. Kapanadze were formed. As noted by D. Sageder, an expert: "Rapid development and development of technologies require not only the naming of new concepts, but also an agreement on the correct and appropriate use of terms. As a practical result of uncompromising scientific "struggles", terminological works began to be organized within certain specialized fields (specialties).

The creation of basic concepts such as "terminological system" (terminological system) and "terminological field" by scientists in the field served as the main criterion for the analysis of the opinions expressed earlier by linguists. In addition, a large number of theoretical and practical definitions began to appear in the light of the term.

It should be noted that at the beginning of the 19th century, lexicographers observed shallow approaches to the expression of the meaning of terminology. In addition, since the 18th century, the word nomenclature has been used in a number of European languages to express the object of a certain field of education. The word nomenclature (Latin nomenclatura) literally means a list of names or a list of

meanings, and is a set of names used to represent research objects in a certain field of science.

Since the functions of terminology and nomenclature terms in linguistics are very close to each other, sometimes it is difficult to distinguish between the two. In this regard, A.D. Khayutin notes that the word nomenclature was first used by the botanist Linnaeus in the sense of "naming, writing" and it was used in the classification of plant names in the field of botany.

Wide use of the word nomenclature and emergence of the word terminology can be observed in the 18th century. Although the various explanations given to define nomenclature and terminology appear close and similar in the studied sources, we can see that the functional-semantic distinction of nomenclature versus term is clarified in the latest published encyclopedic and explanatory dictionaries.

Based on the principle of modern understanding, "term" is a word and word that expresses a clear understanding in certain fields (sports, economy, legislation, law, art, finance, literature, politics, education, diplomacy, etc.) and performs a special functional task. From the semantic point of view, the term is a lexical unit limited to the scope of a special field. However, there is also the fact that in some cases, the terms of a certain field undergo the process of integration into the terminology of another field, as a result, they also serve as additional terms for that field. For example, the term morphology in linguistics is understood as a branch of linguistics. This term means "structure of the human body (organism)" in the field of medicine, "structure of the animal body and cell structure" in zoology, "structural structure of plants" in botany, and "subsoil layers and resources, mountain" in the field of geology. The structure of genders" expresses such meanings. The term stone is a natural body in the field of ecology. It represents a unit of measurement in the fields of finance, taxation, economy. In the field of sports, it means a heavy weapon that develops muscles.

One of the most important principles of the naming process is that it is desirable to fully illuminate the generalized image and essence of the named object through a concrete expression or symbol. In other words, it is necessary to move from specificity to generality. As a result, the nomination process, in addition to the processes of definition and generalization, performs functions such as learning or teaching (fully illuminating and correctly delivering the information represented by the language form). This process is also available in English and Uzbek languages. For example: handball - handball, water polo - water polo, table tennis - table tennis, low kick - low kick, long distance - long distance. In these examples, information about both the object and the sign is given at the same time through the nomination process of concepts related to noun, adjective and verb word groups.

Naturally, there is a continuous connection between language and society. Over time, objects and concepts of real reality in society acquire a new name, and the old ones in most cases fall out of use or undergo a semantic change in the process of use. As a result, the language will have wider lexical possibilities. These factors play a key role in the emergence of the primary and secondary principles of nomination, and we can observe this reality in both languages.

The nomination of terms related to the field of sports has its own characteristics. In the nominative process aimed at a certain goal, taking the name of a specific object through terminological units, based on the characteristics of sports, is of particular importance in this field.

Nowadays, as a result of the competition and development of science and technology, new real and unrealistic scientific concepts are constantly emerging, increasing the need for nomination. Physiologically and psychologically, a person has the ability to produce intellectual property (product) with the help of nominative activity, and becomes a consumer of the product produced by him. As the weight of intellectual property increases, human language becomes such a tool that a person cannot do any activity without this tool. It follows that the nominative activity of a person is of incomparable importance in terms of understanding the world.

Each nation has its own national sports, and these sports fight as much as possible for their development and prosperity. As examples of national sports that have developed in recent times, we can mention English cricket, Scottish curling, Japanese sumo, Indonesian pinchaak-silat, Thai muay thai, and Uzbek wrestling. As such sports become more popular, nomination processes improve based on certain nominative criteria and principles of the language. In this sense, a new concept and any new word or term related to the field of sports arises for four different pragmatic reasons:

Primary nomination means to express or name concepts and things that appear in real reality through primary words. In modern linguistics, relatively little information is given about this phenomenon. It can be determined mainly through etymological and scientific analysis. We observe examples of the primary nomination related to the field of sports in the example of brands (trademarks, company brands). For example: Adidas - Adidas, Reebok - Reebok. If the brand name is duplicated, it will not belong to the primary category. For example: puma - puma (the name of a large wild cat).

Due to the fact that the principle of secondary nomination is widespread in our language and has a polyfunctionality, it has been given different definitions by linguists. According to S. Makarova, "this is the use of old words for the need of long-term use of the new denomination."

I. Shuvalov noted that "existing nominative means in the language can be used through new naming functions, besides, they have specific characteristics of the language unit and the speech unit."

1) the process of creating sports terms includes the pragmatic parameters of the person who creates them (to which social group a person belongs: his mental and spiritual, emotional state);

2) in the process of acceptance of a new concept (word or term) as a speech unit, pragmatic factors related to the processes of receiving it play an important role;

3) focusing on the use of a new concept (word or term) in context as a linguistic unit, and not ignoring the additional, pragmatic and relevant semantic aspects present in its semantic scope;

4) formation of a lexical unit according to the necessary needs of the language is the most important.

In recent years, the acceleration of this field, the emergence of new types of sports, and the continuous appearance of terms and neologisms in the field have caused some problems related to the activity of language nominations. In this process, it can be said that mixed, complex, crazy and tangled concepts are emerging. In order to prevent this situation, it is advisable to regulate sports lexicon in English and Uzbek languages, unify terminological units, and develop rules for their proper application based on certain criteria. Based on this, lexical units related to sports can be classified and grouped according to the principles of nomination in the following form

1. Representing the concept of a thing or object in the field of sports

nominations: belt - card (yellow, red), whistle - whistle, lappak - discus, tishqolip - outhpiece, tros - line (rope, cable), tape - ribbon (stripe), carpet (mat) - carpet (mat), krasovka - sneakers, core - shot (rounded iron ball), sled - sleigh (sled), rifle - rifle, brand (sign, badge) - emblem, canoe - canoe, springboard - springboard.

2. Nominations expressing the concept of a person or participant in the field of sports: referee - defender, defender - hockey player, rider - rider (jockey), fan - fan (supporter), secondant - secondant, reviewer - commentator, coach - coach (trainer), cleaner, starter, leader, leader.

3. Nominations expressing the concept of movement in the field of sports: kick - to kick (hit), block - to block (save), attack - to attack, mark - to determine (mark), start - to start (begin), whistle to whistle, to bow, to shoot, to bend, to intensify, to applaud, to break.

4. Nominations expressing the concept of place in the field of sports: field - field (pitch), cabin - cabin, arena - arena, court - cort, ring - ring, cage - cage, camp -

camp, lawn - lawn (turf), stadium - stadium, velotrack - velo-track, water basin (pool) - pool, minbar (audience pulpit, tribune) - tribune (stand).

5. Nominations representing sports in the field of sports: football, wrestling, boxing, running, swimming, fencing, mountain skiing, sea racing (marine) racing.

6. Mixed nominations in sports: record, tournament, tournament, power (force, strength), skills, water (sport), ice palace (ice sports complex), physical condition - psychological condition, space speed, sports time, sports hygiene, VAR (video assistant referee) system, election, AFC (Asian Football Confederation) AFC (Asian Football Confederation), national association - national federation.

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